

Adaptive human tracking using wearable sensors

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Abstract—In the last decade, the indoor localization and positioning has gained attention. The development of location based service, such as activity monitoring during training, has been one of the main drivers for this interest. In this contribution, a tracking system based on inertial measurement is proposed. The tracking system is designed for human tracking. The system has been designed to be low cost and self-configurable. To this aim, the system is able to learn all the parameters exploited in the computation. Moreover, the computational load of the system is low, so it can be implemented over wearable devices. The proposed approach has been tested in a real scenario and preliminary results are reported.

I. INTRODUCTION

Indoor and outdoor localization is very important in many fields, such as robotics, assistive technology, tourism, industry monitoring, sport, and also in risky operations such as firefighters interventions. Nowadays, inertial sensors are used in many applications, for example, human motion monitoring or pedestrian positioning; however, there are limitations that cause data drift in the process and low accuracy. Pedestrian Dead Reckoning (PDR) is the process of estimating position using a previously estimated or measured position and updating it using velocity and trajectory updates. PDR, although it may show drift, is widely used when GPS fails or is unavailable or its accuracy is not sufficient.

In [1] an analysis of available PDR methods with a focus on wearable sensors is presented and a comparison of the accuracy of different sensor layouts and algorithms is shown. The aim of this work is to improve a positioning system for human tracking. Specifically we propose a learning technique where all parameters are identified and estimated online, so the algorithm is independent from the user (i.e., weight, gender, height) and from the system calibration (i.e., accelerometer bias, positions of the anchors, magnetometer calibration, and so on). A situation awareness is also on line estimated to improve the performance of the tracking system. A recursive adaptive identification procedure is implemented, and new acquisitions or new calibration data are used to improve the parametric estimate without losing what has been done previously. Moreover, the algorithm is designed to reduce the evaluation time and no time consuming black box machine learning algorithm is required.

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In the followings, the proposed adaptive tracking system is detailed and some preliminary results are reported.

II. ADAPTIVE TRACKING SYSTEM

The tracking system has been developed to compute the position of human in the space. Thus, the output of the tracking system is the vector \hat{x}_i composed by the position coordinates and the orientation of the human in a planar environment. For this purpose, the human is equipped with a wearable device, consisting of an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) and a magnetometer. The wearable device is placed on the back of the human, near the center of mass, having the vertical axis of the BF aligned with the human’s coronal plane, perpendicular to the floor. It is worth noticing that the IMU and magnetometer data are measured according to a moving coordinate frame, i.e. the IMU *body frame* (BF), while the tracking is computed with respect to a global coordinate frame (GF)

The Adaptive Tracking System is composed by two main modules, the learning module and the tracking filter. As sketched in Fig.1, they run in parallel: the learning module continuously adapt the parameters of the the filter, while the tracking filter compute the pose of the human.

A. Tracking filter

The tracking filter computes the position of the human exploiting the measurements from IMU and magnetometer. Specifically, two different activities are detected (*standing still* and *motion*) by analyzing a set of samples from the accelerometer and gyroscopes. The covariances of the set of measurement are computed and compared with the thresholds $\text{cov}(m_j, m_{j+1}, \dots, m_{j+k}) \leq t_m$ where m_j is the measurement and t_m is the correspondent threshold. If one of the tow covariance values is lower than the threshold, the activity is classified as *standing still*, otherwise *motion*. The cardinality of the measurement sets k is updated during the experiment. It is worth noticing that a covariance computed over a large number of measurement is more accurate, however this also introduces a delay in the position computation. Therefore, the choice of k represents a tradeoff between accuracy and delay. This choice is based on the activity motion: specifically, $k = 3l$ where l is the number of measurement samples retrieved during a single step event. Once the activity is recognized, the position of the human can be computed. If *motion* activity is detected, a Kalman filter is adopted to merge information from the IMU and the magnetometer according the following equations. The prediction step is computed by updating the position and the orientation of the human according to the displacement

Fig. 1. Tracking system architecture

computed in the step event and the angular velocity from the gyroscopes, specifically

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{i|i-1} &= \mathbf{f}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{i-1|i-1}, \bar{\omega}_i) = \\
 &= \mathbf{A}\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{i-1|i-1} + \begin{bmatrix} \Delta s_i \cos \theta_{i-1|i-1} \\ \Delta s_i \sin \theta_{i-1|i-1} \\ (\bar{\omega}_i - b_\omega)\Delta t_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (1) \\
 \mathbf{P}_{i|i-1} &= \mathbf{J}_x^f \mathbf{P}_{i-1|i-1} \mathbf{J}_x^{fT} + \mathbf{Q}_i
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3}$, $\bar{\omega}_i$ is the mean angular velocity computed on the samples collected during the step event, Δs_i is step length, Δt_i is the duration of the step event, b_{ω} the gyro bias, $\mathbf{P}_{i|i-1}$ is the prediction covariance matrix, and \mathbf{J}_x^f is the Jacobian of $\mathbf{f}(\cdot)$ with respect to $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$. The magnetometer provide information about the orientation of the human, $\varphi_{i,M}$. Thus, the expected measurement can be modeled as

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}}_i = \mathbf{C} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{i|i-1} = [0 \ 0 \ 1] \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{i|i-1}. \quad (2)$$

The update equations become

$$\begin{aligned}
 s_i &= \mathbf{C} \mathbf{P}_{i|i-1} \mathbf{C}^T + r_i \\
 \mathbf{k}_i &= \mathbf{P}_{i|i-1} \mathbf{C}^T s_i^{-1} \\
 \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{i|i} &= \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{i-1|i-1} + \mathbf{k}_i (\varphi_{i,M} - \mathbf{C} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{i-1|i-1}) \\
 \mathbf{P}_{i|i} &= (\mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} - \mathbf{k}_i \mathbf{C}) \mathbf{P}_{i-1|i-1}
 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where r_i is the covariance that model the uncertainties of the magnetometer measurements. If the standing still is detected, the position is computed as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{i|i} &= \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{i-1|i-1} \\
 \mathbf{P}_{i|i} &= \mathbf{P}_{i-1|i-1}
 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

B. Learning module

The learning module adapts all the parameters of the tracking filter during the motion. Specifically, it performs the calibration for the magnetometer, updates the IMU bias and computes all the parameter for identify and compute the human displacement.

Consumer-grade magnetometers are prone to several errors. These errors can be divided into instrumentation errors and magnetic deviation. The former depend on the device and are represented by scale factors, bias, and non-orthogonality of the axes. The magnetic deviations depends on the ferromagnetic features of the environment. They can be classified as hard iron and soft iron: the first can be modeled as bias, the second as scale factor. By combined the instrumentation errors and the magnetic deviation, the vector of measurements \mathbf{h}_m retrieved by the magnetometer can be written as $\mathbf{h}_E = \mathbf{C} \mathbf{h}_m + \mathbf{g}$ where \mathbf{h}_E is the vector of the Earth magnetic field, the matrix \mathbf{C} encodes the scale factors, the non-orthogonality and the soft iron errors, and \mathbf{g} is the vector of the bias and hard iron errors. When magnetometer measurements are not affected by perturbations, the norm of the magnetometer vector is equal to the magnitude of the Earth's magnetic field. When the magnetometer rotates in space, the collected measurements should lie on a ellipsoid. Considering this constraint, the calibration parameters, i.e., the matrix \mathbf{C} and the vector \mathbf{g} , can be easily retrieved by using an ellipsoid fitting algorithm [2]. Considering only the measurement in the (x, y) -plane of the BF, the calibration reduces to finding the parameter that fits a ellipse. The fitting procedure is repeated during the experiment to improve the

accuracy of the calibration and therefore the reliability of the magnetometer data.

Concerning the IMU bias, it is well known that they slowly changes over time, due to the temperature and the operating conditions. To this aim the bias of the accelerometer and the gyroscopes are updated during standing still event. They are computed as $b = \text{avg}(m_j, m_{j+1}, \dots, m_{j+k})$. Once estimated, the bias is eliminated from the corresponding measurement. Following this approach, the gravity acceleration is also removed since it can be considered as a bias along the z -axis of the BF.

Concerning the motion activities, the adaptive module computes the step length. To determine the step length Δs_i , the dynamic approach proposed in [3] is considered, thus the displacement Δs at each step event i becomes

$$\Delta s_i = \beta \sqrt[4]{a_{M,i} - a_{m,i}} \quad (5)$$

where β is a parameter that depends on gender, weight, and height of the human, while $a_{M,n}$ and $a_{m,n}$ are the maximum and minimum accelerations along the z -axis of the GF retrieved during the step event i . The displacement depends on the accelerations in the step event, which change when the human is walking or running. The number of sample l in a step event change according to the motion speed and it is also use to determine the activity. The parameter l is initialized by considering the IMU sampling frequency and the average step frequency in human walking (i.e., 1.5Hz). To adaptively compute it, a procedure to identify $a_{M,n}$ and $a_{m,n}$ and zero crossing over the accelerometer data is implemented. This procedure allows to isolate a single step and therefore the parameter l .

III. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

The proposed approach has been validated in real scenario. Here, only a significant experiment are reported for sake of space. In the first experiment, the human moves along the halfway line of a soccer field. The human starts the experiment with a standing still activity lasting 15s, thereafter reaches the opposite sideline, turns back, and stops for 10s. Finally, he comes back to the starting position. The overall length of the path is 130 m. During the experiment, the human changes the walking speed, so the IMU processing needs to adapt the parameters to accurately compute the displacement.

The result of the activity detection is reported in Tab. I, where positive is the activity *motion* and negative is the activity *standing still*. A quantitative analysis is proposed based on the classification error: specifically, the accuracy, the sensitivity, the specificity, the positive predictive value (PPV), and the negative predictive value (NPV) is reported in Tab. II. As it can be seen, the activities are correctly classified and the classifier shows an optimal predictive capability for positive events (i.e., motion), while the standing still activity results more difficult to detect. This depends on i) the limited

Fig. 2. Acceleration along coronal axes of the human during standing still event, triangles identify false negative

duration of the standing still activity with respect to the motion one (i.e., there are less events to be classified as standing still) ii) the residual errors during activity switching. For example, some steps are recognized when the human is standing still before start, as highlighted in Fig. 2 due to the adaptive threshold.

TABLE I
ACTIVITY DETECTION OUTCOME

True P	False P	True N	False N
259	5	34	7

TABLE II
PERFORMANCES OF THE ACTIVITY DETECTION

Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV
96%	97%	87%	98%	83%

TABLE III
ERROR COMPARISON

Tracking Algorithm	Final err	Mean err	Min err	Max err
PDR	0.84	0.13	0.01	2.53

According to ISO/IEC 18305 standard we evaluate the localization error when the user stops and at starting position. When user stops the mean error is about 15 cm. The final localization error is about 90 cm.

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